

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABUBAKAR bearing USN 6SU19PT001 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANJAL K bearing USN 6SU19PT002 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsAROMAL SURESH bearing USN 6SU19PT003 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsATHULYA K bearing USN 6SU19PT004 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsCHRISTO CHACKO ABRAHAM bearing USN 6SU19PT005 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsGEORGE SAJU bearing USN 6SU19PT006 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/MsMIDHUN MATHEWS bearing USN 6SU19PT007has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED SHABEER bearing USN 6SU19PT008 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED AJAS B bearing USN 6SU19PT009 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsMUSAB bearing USN 6SU19PT010 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsNANDANA BABU N bearing USN 6SU19PT011has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIKTHA L C bearing USN 6SU19PT012 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsPOOJA VISWAS bearing USN 6SU19PT013 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsPUNNYA MADHU C bearing USN 6SU19PT014has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PUNYA PRAKASH bearing USN 6SU19PT015 has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre, Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSADIYA SIDHEEK bearing USN 6SU19PT016has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsSREELAKSHMI A bearing USN 6SU19PT017has completed his/her Internship at Srinivas institute of medical sciences and research centre ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Perfusion Technology programme for the academic year 2019-20.

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